

The Plum Village Sangha of Thich Nhat Hanh

By Brooke Schedneck, Rhodes College

Entry tags: Southeast Asian Religions, Vietnam, Vietnamese Religions, Religious Group, Buddhist Traditions

The Plum Village Sangha of Thich Nhat Hanh consists of ten monastic practice centers, three in the USA, one in Australia, one in Hong Kong, one in Thailand, and four in France. The Plum Village monastic practice center was founded in 1982 by Vietnamese monk Thich Nhat Hanh. All of his centers house resident monks and nuns ordained in the Plum Village tradition of Thich Nhat Hanh, and host multiple retreats, courses, and days of mindfulness throughout the year for the lay members of the community.

Date Range: 1982 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Vietnam, Hong Kong, Germany, France, Australia, Thailand, USA

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, Hong Kong Special Administration Region, Europe, Western Europe, France, United States, Southeast Asia, Germany, Vietnam

This map reflects the proximate centers of Plum Village Monasteries in the school of Thích Nhất Hạnh's teachings of Engaged Buddhism. The locations are in France, Germany, the United States (New York, California, and Mississippi), Australia, Hong Kong, and Thailand. As Thích Nhất Hạnh's teachings have achieved broad popularity in key urban centers in Vietnam, even though no official centers were ever established, another polygon represents the proximate location of his ordination site in Huế.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: *Fragrant Palm Leaves: Journals 1962-1966*, Thich Nhat Hanh
- Source 2: *Learning True Love: Practicing Buddhism in a Time of War*, Sister Chan Khong
- Source 3: *True Virtue: The Autobiography of a Western Buddhist Nun*, Sister Annabel Laity

Notes: There are very few secondary sources on Thich Nhat Hanh, perhaps because he has written so much himself. Because of this, the best print sources for understanding the Plum Village tradition are from Thich Nhat Hanh himself and his followers. I have listed here memoirs of himself and his practitioners as some of the best ways to understand the philosophy and development of these communities.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://plumvillage.org/>
- Source 1 Description: The Plum Village headquarters website has many resources on mindfulness, practices of the Plum Village tradition, and information on the various centers.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.parallax.org/>
- Source 2 Description: This is the press of Thich Nhat Hanh's books and others within the Plum Village community.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.mindfulnessbell.org/>
- Source 3 Description: The Mindfulness Bell is a newsletter containing resources for practitioners within the Plum Village tradition.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://thichnhatanhfoundation.org/>
- Source 1 Description: This is the foundation for the works and donations to the community
- Source 2 URL: <https://walkwithmefilm.com/>
- Source 2 Description: This is a link to a documentary about Plum Village

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Thich Nhat Hanh uses the Pali Canon and Mahayana Buddhist scriptures in creating his practices for the community.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: There is a chanting book, which is used during retreats and Days of Mindfulness. These chants and scriptures are used for ceremonies. There are also lots of practice songs, which followers love to sing.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

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↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

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Notes: If necessary, monastics can choose which chants to follow for a retreat. But the authoritative nature of early Buddhist scriptures is not alterable.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

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↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

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Notes: In order to write authoritatively about Buddhist scriptures, one would have to be a monastic or high level dharma teacher, appointed and recognized by Thich Nhat Hanh, if they were a lay follower. Not just anyone within the community could write about their interpretation of Buddhist scriptures.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The monastics of the Plum Village community would transmit the practices of Thich Nhat Hanh. These practices are based on the scriptures. For example, the practice of Beginning Anew is based on the pavarana recitation and confession of monks from the Vinaya of the Pali Canon. Sister Chan Khong, *Beginning Anew*, Parallax Press, 2015.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The codified canon of scriptures exists within the Buddhist tradition, however, Thich Nhat Hanh takes from both sects of Theravada and Mahayana in his reinterpretations of scriptures, when creating his practices.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: This is a transnational and international Buddhist community, which originated in Vietnam. In their centers in Hong Kong and Thailand, there is competition from other kinds of Buddhism, such as Chinese and Theravada. In USA, Australia, and Europe, Buddhism is considered a foreign religion, and would have competition from the more mainstream religions of Protestant Christianity, especially. Although the Plum Village monastic practice centers limit

their use of Buddhism, and make their practices appealing to all religions, they are still a Buddhist center, with roots in Buddhism. Because of this, they have competition from the dominant religious groups in each region.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The Plum Village community tries to accommodate all different religions in their retreats and Days of Mindfulness. There is openness to other religions. Thich Nhat Hanh, as the founder of Plum Village community, has especially been in dialogue with Christianity. This can be seen in one of his most well-known books: *Living Buddha, Living Christ*, Riverhead Books, 1996.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: The cultural contact is open and accommodating from the perspective of the Plum Village community.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: There are few monuments at the monastic practice centers of Plum Village communities. In Magnolia Grove, for example, there is one Buddha statue in the main Rising Tide Meditation Hall and there is a large monument of Thich Nhat Hanh meeting Martin Luther King, Jr. However, I believe that most of the practice centers would simply have a statue of the Buddha. There are not any statues of Thich Nhat Hanh or his followers, to my knowledge.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 700

Notes: There are over 700 monastics in the Plum Village communities.

<https://plumvillage.org/about/becoming-a-monastic/>

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Anyone can join the Plum Village community by attending retreats or days of mindfulness. These community members might decide to make a commitment to the practice of Plum Village by taking the Five Mindfulness Trainings. This is a formal ceremony usually conducted at the end of a retreat at a monastic practice center. For a deeper religious affiliation, the Plum Village Community has two levels of ordination. One is a lay ordination in the Order of Interbeing. Committed individuals remain in regular society but live by the 14 Mindfulness Trainings. For those seeking a deeper commitment, Plum Village monastic centers ordain monastics who would like to live their life in a center, being cared for by the monastic and lay community, and giving back through serving others. Information on the Order of Interbeing:

<https://plumvillage.org/about/order-of-interbeing/> The 14 Mindfulness Trainings are described in detail in Thich Nhat Hanh's *Interbeing: Fourteen Guidelines for Engaged Buddhism*, Parallax Press, 1998. The 5 Mindfulness Trainings are described in Thich Nhat Hanh's *The Mindfulness Survival Kit: Five Essential Practices*, Parallax Press, 2013.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: Even children can take the 5 Mindfulness Trainings as long as they are old enough to understand the commitment they are making. For ordination, one must be over 18, unless the aspirant has permission from their parents. <https://plumvillage.org/about/becoming-a-monastic/>

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: There are both female and male monastics in the Plum Village community. They use the title Sister and Brother.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The receiving of the mindfulness trainings are conducted in a formal ritual usually conducted after a retreat at a monastic practice center. The ordination as a monastic is more rare and would be determined based on the individual and when they and the practice center are ready.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Within the monastic practice centers there are halls for gathering and chanting and meditating together. There are also Buddha statues and one statue of Thich Nhat Hanh and Martin Luther King, Jr. at Magnolia Grove practice center in USA, which was mentioned above. In the meditation halls are altars filled with flowers, for the most part, as well as calligraphy written by Thich Nhat Hanh. He has written phrases to remind people to be mindful, such as "Present Moment, Wonderful Moment" and "Breath, My Dear."

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no way to know the percentage of people within the sample region who are participants in the Plum Village communities. There is more of a fluid group of supporters from all over the world who could come to any retreat at any of the centers. There is not a bounded nature to this transnational community.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Plum Village community is open for others to join. They actively proselytize their teachings and ability to join, but this is not mandated or coercive. I have attended retreats where the monastics opened the possibility of joining and ordaining to the people present. They would be happy to have more people ordain into the Order of Interbeing, or as a monastic, and help to spread the practices of Thich Nhat Hanh. His books also serve as a way to proselytize. The monastics see their teachings as being able to help everyone and the world so of course they want to recruit more people to join.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: There is no official political support for Plum Village in any of the monastic practice centers where they are located. In fact, there is negative political support in Vietnam. This is why although the tradition began there, there is no monastic practice center able to be supported in Vietnam.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: There is at least one icon of Thich Nhat Hanh and if one counts the Buddha as a human, then there are images of him throughout the monastic practice centers.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: This is a large official religious group, with its large monastic practice centers. However, because there are only ten of these centers spread out over 3 continents, there are many smaller sanghas in local areas anyone can join. Adherents usually refresh their practice with a retreat at a monastic practice center at least once a year. <https://plumvillage.org/community/>.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Notes: The sacred sites are connected to the life of the Buddha. Thich Nhat Hanh visited the sites of the Buddha's life in India with many of his disciples. As well, many of his disciples consider his root temple in Hanoi to be a sacred location in the life of their teacher.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Thich Nhat Hanh is the clear leader of the Plum Village community, although Sister Chan Khong is almost his equal in terms of her stature in the community. Since Thich Nhat Hanh has not died, there is no way to know how the next leader will be chosen. I imagine the communities will stop having one leader and there will emerge many leaders from all of the monastic practice centers. All of the monastics who give dharma talks to the communities and write books, will continue to be leaders of the Plum Village community. Biography of Thich Nhat Hanh is found on the Plum Village website: <https://plumvillage.org/about/thich-nhat-hanh/>.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: Thich Nhat Hanh is acknowledged to be able to make mistakes within the community. However, Thich Nhat Hanh would himself acknowledge this. Although there is hierarchy to the monastic structure, the monastic practice centers themselves are run in a democratic way, with all the monastic community involved.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

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↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

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Notes: No, adherents are invited to come and see the practice for themselves. They are able to question Thich Nhat Hanh's teachings in the retreats and monastics attempt to explain clearly his teachings and the benefit of the practices. The practitioners can decide for themselves what is helpful. Those who find it helpful will return and those who do not, will not become a follower.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Notes: Thich Nhat Hanh has led pilgrimages to India with his close monastics and lay followers. A group also took on a pilgrimage to Vietnam to visit Thich Nhat Hanh's homeland in 2005. See John Chapman, "The 2005 Pilgrimage and Return to Vietnam of Exiled Zen Master Thich Nhat Hanh."

Membership/Group Interactions

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↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

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Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

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Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

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written phrases to remind people to be mindful, such as "Present Moment, Wonderful Moment" and "Breath, My Dear."

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↳ Cemeteries:
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↳ Altars:
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– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:
– On persons
– Only religious public space

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– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):
– Yes

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↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

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Notes: The sacred sites are connected to the life of the Buddha. Thich Nhat Hanh visited the sites of the Buddha's life in India with many of his disciples. As well, many of his disciples consider his root temple in Hanoi to be a sacred location in the life of their teacher.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Notes: Thich Nhat Hanh has led pilgrimages to India with his close monastics and lay followers. A group also took on a pilgrimage to Vietnam to visit Thich Nhat Hanh's homeland in 2005. See John Chapman, "The 2005 Pilgrimage and Return to Vietnam of Exiled Zen Master Thich Nhat Hanh."

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Plum Village communities offer social norms that all of society should aim for, such as loving speech, loving-kindness, compassion, and understanding towards others and ourselves.

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: The only beings, which are discussed in the Plum Village tradition, which are non-human, are bodhisattvas. There are chants in their chanting booklet praising the qualities of bodhisattvas.

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Notes: Thich Nhat Hanh's Plum Village does not often discuss rebirth. In his book on death, *No Death, No Fear: Comforting Wisdom for Life*, Thich Nhat Hanh discusses how we become part of nature when we die and that we can see loved ones in the flowers and trees.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Notes: Thich Nhat Hanh's Plum Village does not often discuss rebirth. In his book on death, *No Death, No Fear: Comforting Wisdom for Life*, Thich Nhat Hanh discusses how we become part of nature when we die and that we can see loved ones in the flowers and trees.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: The only beings, which are discussed in the Plum Village tradition, which are non-human, are bodhisattvas. There are chants in their chanting booklet praising the qualities of bodhisattvas.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Plum Village communities offer social norms that all of society should aim for, such as loving speech, loving-kindness, compassion, and understanding towards others and ourselves.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Only for monastic members of the Plum Village community. Celibacy is not required for those ordained as lay members of the Order of Interbeing.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: For lay members the precept against sexual misconduct is followed. This restricts sexual activity not causing harm, but is not necessarily requiring monogamy.

Monogamy (males):

– No

Monogamy (females):

– No

Other sexual constraints (males):

– No

Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: In the Plum Village tradition, they even have dinner! Although they are vegetarian and mostly vegan meals.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: It is not a taboo but meat is not allowed in these communities.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: One would give up personal belongings only if one were going to be ordained as a monastic in the tradition.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Ordained members of the Order of Interbeing should attend a mindfulness retreat once a year and attend a Day of Mindfulness once a month.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The monastics accept hundreds of precepts, the lay ordained members accept 14 and regular practitioners commit to 5 ethical precepts.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: One is expected to practice mindfulness in one's home and daily life.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: Participation is not required but members are encouraged to attend the Buddhist holiday celebrations at monastic practice centers.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: Only dress is changed to monastic robes for those fully ordained and a brown jacket is worn for those in the Order of Interbeing.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: All the monastics are called sister and brother, while the lay supporters are usually called aunts and uncles.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Only for monastic members of the Plum Village community. Celibacy is not required for those ordained as lay members of the Order of Interbeing.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: For lay members the precept against sexual misconduct is followed. This restricts sexual activity not causing harm, but is not necessarily requiring monogamy.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

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– No

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– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: One would give up personal belongings only if one were going to be ordained as a monastic in the tradition.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Ordained members of the Order of Interbeing should attend a mindfulness retreat once a year and attend a Day of Mindfulness once a month.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The monastics accept hundreds of precepts, the lay ordained members accept 14 and regular practitioners commit to 5 ethical precepts.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: One is expected to practice mindfulness in one's home and daily life.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: Participation is not required but members are encouraged to attend the Buddhist holiday celebrations at monastic practice centers.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

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– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: All the monastics are called sister and brother, while the lay supporters are usually called aunts and uncles.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: They are a group of linked communities and branches of Plum Village, which was created by Thich Nhat Hanh.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a Thich Nhat Hanh Foundation, which manages the funds for the groups. Otherwise the monastics govern themselves according to democratic principles.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: They purchase food for themselves at the grocery store.

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They would interact with their nation-state's institutions.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: They are a group of linked communities and branches of Plum Village, which was created by Thich Nhat Hanh.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a Thich Nhat Hanh Foundation, which manages the funds for the groups. Otherwise the monastics govern themselves according to democratic principles.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They would interact with their nation-state's institutions.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: They purchase food for themselves at the grocery store.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Plum Village Sangha of Thich Nhat Hanh, Hanh, Thich Nhat. Living Buddha, Living Christ. Rider, 1996.

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